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Review Article

**IMPACTION OF COMPLIANCE TO INFECTION CONTROL
AMONG HEALTHCARE STAFF**

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Abstract:

Healthcare workers' (HCWs') knowledge of infection prevention and control (IPC) methods is critical for effective IPC. Compliance with IPC guidelines have serious consequences for HCW safety, patient safety, and the care environment. This study was carried out by scanning the literature through electronic databases such as Medline, Embase, and PubMed for all relevant papers published up to the beginning of 2023. The nursing home environment is extremely permissive to infection acquisition and spread because susceptible residents share sources of air, food, water, and health care inside an institutional setting. To help enhance nurse knowledge and attitudes toward infection prevention, an educational program should be created. Adopting a diverse approach to IPC improvement intervention tactics has been found to minimize HAIs and enhance HCW compliance with IPC procedures.

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INTRODUCTION:

Healthcare personnel, particularly physicians and nurses, form the backbone of any country's healthcare system. Failure to protect them from infection while caring for their patients has a detrimental influence on overall patient care and puts their health at risk [1]. Despite the WHO's interim guidance on infection prevention and control (IPC) methods given in March 2020, a significant proportion of HCWs have been infected since the start of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. Furthermore, multiple studies have proved the usefulness of using personal protective equipment (PPE) appropriately in preventing infection while treating patients. As a result, HCWs' compliance with IPC instructions must be enforced in order to protect a functional health system by lowering infection rates among front-line staff [2,3].

Compliance, defined as how closely a person follows instructions, is critical to infection prevention but has been found to be unsatisfactory among HCWs in the pre-pandemic era [4,5]. Even after the epidemic began, HCWs' IPC behavior was found to be inadequate in some nations. Several issues have been recognized as contributing to HCWs' low adherence to IPC practices, including a lack of protective tools, inadequate recommendations on how to utilize them, increasing workload, weariness, and so on [6,7,8]. Theory-based examination of human behavior can be used to improve HCWs' adherence to IPC practices. Indeed, some scholars used psychological theories to investigate HCWs' IPC behavior during the prepandemic era. However, substantial theory-based investigations on HCWs' IPC behavior during the present COVID-19 epidemic are still lacking [9]. It can be challenging to maintain infection control behaviors. Previous research has found that the general community has difficulty adhering to protective behaviors such as wearing facemasks, using hand sanitizing gel, and quarantining during infectious disease outbreaks [10,11]. In the general population, the main facilitators of compliance appear to be perceived susceptibility, perceived severity of being afflicted, and perceived benefits of compliance, as well as accurate knowledge about the disease and recommended behaviors, while major barriers include discomfort, embarrassment, and practical issues [12,13,14].

DISCUSSION:

NHs that provided staff training during both new employee orientation and outbreaks had higher quality urinary catheter use. While previous research has studied the influence of IC professional training on NH quality, none has examined the impact of IC

training on other NH workers to our knowledge. Furthermore, an NH that received IC training at both orientation and during an outbreak may have a more strong IC program. Our findings back up previous data that a targeted and continuous training program was more effective than a single intervention in lowering HAIs [15,16].

Residents with infections must be identified, assessed, and reported by direct patient care workers. These roles necessitate a thorough understanding of IC practices and are critical to the successful deployment of IC processes. Our findings suggest that more comprehensive training may increase staff awareness of IC processes, which is a crucial step toward enhancing overall care quality. Furthermore, urinary catheter use is strongly associated with the development of catheter-associated UTIs in NHs, implying that reinforcing prevention and control processes through timely staff training may be one way to reduce infection rates in NHs, though more research is needed [17,18].

Because many hospitals report high MRSA colonization rates among elderly patients, and because *S. aureus* colonisation rises with age, there are worries about MRSA being introduced into nursing homes by MRSA-positive patients discharged from hospital. When MRSA is introduced, the subsequent spread of MRSA between patients creates a reservoir of MRSA within a nursing home, posing the risk of an outbreak and subsequent hospital outbreaks when infected nursing home residents require hospital care [18,19]. Because of chronic sickness and debilitation, numerous antimicrobial drug exposures, and the presence of pressure ulcers and indwelling devices, nursing homes create an excellent setting for the acquisition and spread of MRSA [20]. MRSA colonization is also a risk factor for death in nursing home residents [20].

The prevalence of Meticillin or methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) within nursing homes is likely to be increasing as a result of the increased prevalence of MRSA within hospitals, which may have been exacerbated by the significant movement of patients from longstay hospitals to communitybased nursing homes. A 1994 research in Birmingham found a frequency of 17% among 191 nursing home residents [21,22]. Surprisingly, phagotyping of the viruses indicated similarities with those found in Birmingham hospitals, implying a direct transfer from hospital to nursing home. A 1999 research in Northamptonshire found a prevalence of 4.7% among 275 residents in 17 nursing homes, with colonized

people in six of the 17 homes [23]. Similar studies in other countries have found MRSA prevalence rates in nursing homes ranging from 1.1% in Germany to 4.9% in Belgium [19], 6.2% in Israel, 8.6% in Ireland, and 22.7% in the United States, however the reason for this disparity is unknown. Recent research has revealed the persistence of high MRSA prevalence rates in nursing homes [24,25,26]. In contrast to the situation in hospitals, little attention has been paid to MRSA infection prevention and control in nursing homes.

There has been substantial discussion regarding how to best prevent and control MRSA transmission. The general opinion is that more appropriate and sensible antibiotic use would aid in combating the rise in antibiotic-resistant bacteria [27]. It is also acknowledged that infection prevention and control techniques play a role in preventing and controlling MRSA spread [27].

Universal precautions (UPs) are a set of treatments and procedures used in the health care context to limit the risk of contracting occupational infections from both known and unknown sources. The primary goals of UPs are to protect personnel from percutaneous injury and to reduce nosocomial infection spread. Students in health care are at greater risk of contracting nosocomial and blood-borne infections. This increased risk can be linked to inadequate adherence to universal infection control procedures, limited clinical knowledge, or a lack of protective supplies [28,29,30]. According to research, medical and health care students do not always wash their hands before and after examining patients. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention⁸ infection prevention guideline, a priority method for infection prevention is periodic assessment of health care workers' knowledge and compliance with infection control guidelines. Several international research studies have evaluated nursing students' knowledge and compliance [31,32]. Great disparities in infection control knowledge and compliance among nursing students have been documented between nations. In Hong Kong, for example, the compliance rate among nursing students was 56.1%. In Jordan, on the other hand, 51.3% of nursing students were rated "excellent" in their understanding of UPs, 39.6% were rated "satisfactory," and 9.1% were rated "weak." In addition, the students' UP practices were judged as "unsafe" (4.1%), "weak" (27.1%), and "competent" (68.8%) [32]. Darawad and AlHussami [34] similarly reported close results, with a mean knowledge score about UPs of 12.3 out of 25 in a sample of Jordanian nursing students. Poor UP knowledge has also been found in industrialized countries such as Italy and Australia, as well as developing countries such as

Namibia [35] and Ghana. [36] Improvements in infection control knowledge and practices following the implementation of educational programs are extensively reported in the literature. In one observational trial, Naderi et al [35] investigated the influence of an educational program on hand cleanliness compliance and the incidence rate of nosocomial infections. The study lasted four years and included nursing and medical professionals who participated in a problem-based instructional program on hand cleanliness.

Wu et al [37] evaluated Taiwanese nursing students' knowledge, application, and confidence in infection prevention precautions and suggested that nursing students take a complete foundation course in infection prevention before entering clinical practice. Nursing students' awareness of hand hygiene was lacking, and their compliance with hand hygiene procedures was inadequate [37]. In response, Celik and Koçasli [38] advocated updating hand hygiene teaching measures. This ignorance could be due to shortcomings in infection prevention teaching provided to nursing students in nursing schools, which frequently leaves students bewildered and unsure about which procedures are appropriate. Nursing schools are regarded to play a significant role in educating nursing students about infection prevention precautions and the need of implementing those precautions in clinical practice, given that approximately 33% of nosocomial infections are avoidable [39,40]. Many research have suggested incorporating hand hygiene education and assessment into the undergraduate curriculum. Other ideas include modifying the nursing training curriculum to include conventional infection prevention precautions and keeping students' infection prevention knowledge current throughout clinical application. Despite the fact that such educational programs could increase nurses' hand hygiene practices, infection prevention practices, and infection prevention knowledge, research studies on educating nursing students on infection prevention precautions are lacking. In Jordan, infection prevention precautions are not taught in nursing school special courses [38,40].

CONCLUSION:

To prevent transmission by skin, it is recommended that efforts be put toward hand cleanliness with antiseptic chemicals and water, rather than simply soap and water. Antiseptic agents should be easily accessible to all healthcare personnel in any situation. In the lack of proper handwashing facilities, a waterless antiseptic product should be utilized. Environmental infection prevention and control

encompasses workplace hygiene, including work surfaces in healthcare settings, as well as the cleanliness of equipment and the disposal of objects that may have come into contact with colonised/infected patients. Role-specific or setting-specific training, emphasizing the importance of protective behaviors and the risk of infection if behaviors are not performed, monitoring of staff behaviors by supervisors and positive reinforcement for correct behaviors, managerial staff leading by example, training focused on the importance and effectiveness of PPE, and better communication of guidelines are all interventions that may be beneficial in improving healthcare workers' compliance.

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